

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe Phase 3

Applications developed by ESIWACE available to users of EuroHPC JU systems via automated deployment platform, including documentation for users, required software stack, automated testing and quality checks
Milestone M1.4

ESiWACE3 Milestone M1.4

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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ESiWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results
<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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Applications developed by ESiWACE available to users of EuroHPC JU systems

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Goals and Governance

The ESiWACE3 consortium agrees to work towards the goal of providing a set of representative applications from the weather and climate community. The objective is to collaborate with CASTIEL2 to ensure the inclusion of these codes in the common repository accessible to EuroHPC JU users. To achieve this goal optimally and without compromising the resources and other commitments of the consortium partners, a set of representative applications and accessible machines has been selected for users. Additionally, the activities required to successfully achieve the goal will be executed through a steering group representing the partners responsible for the selected applications and the HPC centers of the consortium supporting the target machines.

The selected applications are as follows:

- The **HPCW-core**: This includes the High Performance Climate and Weather Benchmark (HPCW)¹ framework and 3 dwarfs of IFS (ectrans, cloudsc, and ecrad). HPCW is constituted by a set of reference codes and the 3 selected dwarfs include modules representative of IFS, one of the most widely used weather applications in Europe from ECMWF². HPCW is chosen because it allows a much more realistic assessment of computational performance of large HPC applications from the domain of climate research and weather forecast systems than current generic benchmarks such as HPL and HPCG. More information about the HPCW-core is contained in the M1.2 document. ECMWF will be responsible with the support of EVIDEN and DKRZ.
- **Autosubmit**³: This application is a workflow manager that allows automating the execution of a weather or climate model runs and it is used by applications such as EC-Earth⁴ or NEMO by different institutions. Autosubmit will be available for the whole EuroHPC ecosystems to simplify the exploitation of the large-scale system for EuroHPC users. BSC will be responsible.
NEMO: the "Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean" (NEMO)⁵ is a state-of-the-art modelling framework. It is used for research activities and forecasting services in ocean and climate sciences. NEMO is developed by a European consortium of 5 partners. The inclusion of NEMO allows the evaluation of a real model by EuroHPC users and the consolidation of its wide adoption in the European area. CMCC will be responsible for it.

¹ <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/hpcw/high-performance-climate-weather-benchmark>

² <https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/documentation-and-support/changes-ecmwf-model>

³ <https://www.bsc.es/research-and-development/software-and-apps/software-list/autosubmit>

⁴ <https://ec-earth.org/>

⁵ <https://www.nemo-ocean.eu/>

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The related steering group has been implemented and organized through the work package 1 (WP1) with representatives from BSC, CMCC, DKRZ, ECMWF and EVIDEN.

The steering group will take the next actions in collaboration with CASTIEL2 and the CICD (Continuous Integration and Continuous Development group organized by Denis Hoppe). The actions planned are:

- Monitoring and guiding the work;
- Synchronizing the work between ESIWACE3 and CASTIEL;
- Discussing strategies with respect to reporting, documenting, deployment and testing on EuroHPC machines.

The steering group will meet quarterly. BSC will coordinate the meetings and meet with CASTIEL2 through the CICD group. Others partners from the steering group will be required for the interaction with CASTIEL2 according to the needs and requirements.

The steering group has agreed on the following roadmap and machines to be included.

EuroHPC platforms chosen

Due to resource constraints and other commitments, ESIWACE3 is devoted to achieve the goal of deploying the aforementioned applications on the three pre-exascale machines in Europe: LUMI, LEONARDO, and Marenostrum5 (MN5). This deployment encompasses both CPU and GPU partitions, depending on the specific requirements of each application.

The aforementioned machines align with ESIWACE primary objective of adapting climate and weather models for exascale computing. Important, all users plan to leverage the consortium applications to exploit these machines, ensuring therefore the successful execution of the primary objective. The selection of these platforms caters to the majority of users interested in running these applications.

Moreover, ESIWACE enjoys the support of BSC and CSC, two of the chosen HPC centers, guaranteeing the success of deploying over these platforms. This support includes an accelerated deployment plan for the new Marenostrum5, anticipated to be available in 2024.

Roadmap

Deployment on EuroHPC machines

The development responsible teams have initiated the deployment of the HPCW-core, Autosubmit, and NEMO on LUMI. Given there is no computational resources provided by the EuroHPC-JU, CSC has collaborated by establishing a project for ESIWACE3 and allocating a few computational resources for compilation and testing. The applications have already been compiled and tested on LUMI, with documentation and compilation recipes readily available. The documentation, along

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with results and deployment instructions for these applications, will be published on the ESiWACE3 website and the GitLab Runner repository provided by CASTIEL and EuroHPC-JU.

Looking ahead, the HPCW-core, Autosubmit, and NEMO could be implemented (or documented if the codes are already running on a system) on the remaining EuroHPC systems. The consideration of additional ESiWACE applications or EuroHPC machines will depend on their availability, access policies, and support provided by the EuroHPC-JU and hosting sites (refer also to the last section).

CICD Group and CASTIEL2 collaboration

ESiWACE3 has become a part of the CICD group organized by CASTIEL2. This group aims to establish a robust and reliable automated deployment process for applications, ensuring that new developments are promptly available to the user communities of EuroHPC JU.

ESiWACE3 actively participates in the monthly meetings, contributing necessary input, including information for CASTIEL Deliverables 2.4 and 5.8. This involves sharing insights about our application codes and experiences in deploying selected applications on LUMI.

ESiWACE3 is committed to support the initiatives of this group and providing the necessary assistance, aligning with the chosen applications and machines outlined in this document. This commitment is undertaken without compromising other planned activities within the Center of Excellence.

Currently, ESiWACE3 is engaged in familiarizing itself with the Gitlab Runner tool and updating our codes in the Gitlab repository⁶.

Possibility to include more applications and EuroHPC machines

BSC will collect inputs from the steering group and the rest of consortium partners to understand the requirements and need from the different partners and user communities to include other applications and deployments over different EuroHPC machines. This information will be provided to JU Program officers to evaluate if additional actions could be considered beyond the roadmap provided in this document.

⁶ <https://codehub.hlrs.de>